

Fracture Toughness on a Thin Film from Plastic Zone

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Abstract

One of the advantages of thin films is its use as a coating that can be applied over a substrate as a protective layer. The application can either be mechanical or chemical, where these fine coatings are exposed to harsh environment. Therefore, quantification of such films are deemed necessary in order to understand the failure mechanisms of the material. Particularly for a thin viscoelastic film with appreciable recovery upon deformation, fracture toughness is difficult to evaluate due to the uncertainties associated with multilayers. Frequently, there exists influence of the substrate or immediate layer present, which shapes the physical properties of thin films. This in turn results in either reduced or compound values during the extraction of experimental data. In order to obtain the absolute value, true specimen must be prepared. However, certain thin films are either expensive or difficult to prepare in bulk condition. Hence, a simpler approach to determine the fracture toughness from plastic zone is proposed by combining in-situ tensile and nanoindentation tests. To the best of the author's knowledge, such approach does not yet exist. The value of poly-phenylenediamine determined from the proposed method and classical extraction method are approximately equal at 2.45 MPa√m and 2.6 MPa√m respectively.

Keywords: Fracture mechanics; Polymers; Thin films; Plasticity; Toughness testing.

1. INTRODUCTION

An important property in material design is fracture toughness, K . It is the resistance to fracture upon inception of cracks, which is used to measure strain energy release rate. Experimentally, the fracture toughness is determined commonly from tensile tests - mode I fracture, which is expressed by:

$$K = \gamma\sqrt{a} \quad (1)$$

where $\gamma = \sigma Y \sqrt{\pi}$ for channel crack, σ = stress, Y = geometrical constant and a = crack length [1].

Similarly, nanoindentation can also be used to determine fracture toughness, which is more suitable for thin films. One of the advantages is that the lower threshold cracks can be observed when compared to micro tests. The fracture toughness [2, 3] of a brittle material is determined from:

$$K = \alpha \left[\frac{E}{H} \right]^{1/2} \left[\frac{P_{max}}{a^{3/2}} \right] \quad (2)$$

$$H = \frac{P_{max}}{A} \quad (3)$$

where α = empirical constant which depends on the geometry of the indenter, E = Young's modulus, H = hardness, P_{max} = maximum load, A = contact area.

For thin film polymers, there exists uncertainty with crack initiations since the material is amorphous and viscoelastic. This is particular for organic coatings in the thickness ranges of few microns with appreciable elastic recovery, where higher thicknesses or free-standing conditions are difficult to obtain.

The uncertainty in in-situ tensile tests are: 1) The crack initiation depends on the substrate, which is accompanied by creep phenomenon. 2) The cracks are influenced by voids and surface energy for a porous substrate. Since the organic coating is viscoelastic, the cracks are often initiated on the substrate underneath the coating or on the opposite surface of the thin film. Hence, stress levels are uncertain in these conditions. Therefore, this work focuses on a simpler approach to determine fracture toughness from plastic zone by combining in-situ tensile and nanoindentation tests.

2. PLASTIC ZONE SIZE

For in-situ tensile, Irwin's model allows determination of plastic zone size [4, 5]. The plastic zone, c for plane-strain condition is given by:

$$c = \frac{1}{3\pi} \left[\frac{K_{IC}}{\sigma_{ys}} \right]^2 \quad (4)$$

where K_{IC} = critical stress intensity factor or fracture toughness. σ_{ys} = yield stress.

In case of nanoindentation, Johnson's model [6] allows determination of plastic zone size from contact parameters. A simple interpretation of Johnson's spherical cavity gives the plastic zone size as [7]:

$$c = \left[\frac{3P}{2\pi\sigma_{ys}} \right]^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

where P = indentation load. This equation was validated with conical tip of various sizes at different contact angles for its angle formulation effectiveness [6].

3. EQUATION

Irwin's and Johnson's models are equated because both theories postulates circular zones and the determination of K follows similar approach i.e., stress-strain is an intrinsic property in all scales – micro or nano. Eq.4 and Eq.5 are reduced from the plastic zone size as given below:

$$\frac{1}{3\pi} \left[\frac{K_{IC}}{\sigma_{ys}} \right]^2 = \left[\frac{3P}{2\pi\sigma_{ys}} \right]^{1/2} \quad (6)$$

$$K_{IC} = \left[\frac{27}{2} \pi P \sigma_{ys}^3 \right]^{1/4} \text{ or} \quad (7)$$

$$K_{IC} \approx 2.5 [P \sigma_{ys}^3]^{0.25} \quad (8)$$

4. SYNTHESIS OF SPECIMEN

The specimen were prepared similar to the techniques used by Alexis RENAUD et al. [8]. The aim was to create a porous surface because it offers a greater interaction with the polymer i.e., mechanical adhesion between the two layers (Fig. a.1). The substrates of aluminium alloy 2024-T3, a common grade used in aeronautical industries for its high fatigue resistance were anodized by a setup in sulfo-tartaric acid electrolytic bath (H₂SO₄ + C₄H₆O₆). The resulting thickness of the substrate were 3µm. As for the polymer, Phenol-paraPhenyleneDiAmine (P-pPDA – Fig. a.2) were prepared by mixing p-phenylenediamine, paraformaldehyde and phenol. P-pPDA layers were then obtained by spin coating at room temperature. The resulting thickness of the organic coatings were 2µm.

Fig. a.1. Schematic of multilayers

Fig. a.2. P-pPDA

5. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

Continuous stiffness measurements (CSM) were performed on thin film (Fig. a.1) in nanoindentation (Fig. b.1) with specimen dimension of 1 cm x 1 cm to extract yield stress using Oliver-Pharr model [9] with Berkovich tip. Here, the CSM were performed through a simple-harmonic oscillator model. This is

more accurate than instrumented indentation because the oscillatory force reduces errors while determining the initial surface contact between the indenter and the specimen. The maximum depth reached on the thin film without the influence of substrate was 50% i.e. 1000 nm. With $\sigma_{ys} = 760$ MPa and corresponding $P = 2.10$ mN, K_{IC} was determined as 2.45 MPa√m using Eq.8.

Fig. b.1. Stress-Strain, nanoindentation

K_{IC} obtained from nanoindentation was then compared with that of in-situ tensile test (Fig. b.2). Here, channel crack analysis were performed under field emission gun (FEG) scanning electron microscope (SEM) on the organic surface (Fig. b.3). The largest crack space was selected because the load is global, which signifies the stresses on the reduced area are presumed to be the same. The crack length, 'a' was measured as 208.3 µm. With $\sigma_{ys} = 116$ MPa and $\sigma = 148$ MPa (Fig. b.4), K_{IC} was determined as 2.6 MPa√m using Eq.1.

Fig. b.2. Specimen's geometry – In-situ tensile test

Fig. b.3. Channel cracks on P-pPDA, Al 2024

Fig. b.4. Stress-strain, In-situ tensile – Al 2024 multilayer

6. DISCUSSIONS

- Although extensive literature on P-pPDA is not available, the values were similar when compared with other cross-linking polymers such as polycarbonates, where $K_{IC} = 2.2$ MPa [10]. Akono et al. [11] presented that microscopic

fracture toughness is twice than macroscopic fracture toughness by scratch tests. Whereas, the K_{IC} determined in this technique using the modified equation (Eq.8) in nanoindentation is approximately equal to K_{IC} from in-situ tensile test.

Fig. c.1. Channel cracks on P-pPDA, Al 1050

- To support these arguments, in-situ tensile tests were performed on non-anodized T3 Al 1050 spin-coated with P-pPDA. The absence of anodic layer signifies the absence of strong mechanical adhesion between rough anodic layer and P-pPDA. Therefore the failure of the coating depends

directly on the ductile material underneath. In this case, $\sigma_{ys} = 59$ MPa which was less than half of Al 2024 multilayer, yet cracks were rapidly growing. With $a = 403.9 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig c.1) and $\sigma = 60$ MPa (Fig. c.2), K_{IC} was determined as $2.14 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ using Eq.1.

Fig. c.2. Stress-strain, In-situ tensile – Al 1050 multilayer

- Therefore, K_{IC} determined (Eq.1) from two different in-situ tensile tests has a variation of $\pm 0.4 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$. However, K_{IC} from nanoindentation (Eq.8) lies within this variation. This signifies K_{IC} is approximate when P at yield point is chosen in nanoindentation experiment.

7. CONCLUSION

K_{IC} of P-pPDA was determined as $2.45 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ using a modified equation (Eq.8) from plastic zone. The value of K_{IC} from two different in-situ tensile tests (Eq.1) were approximately equal. This approach is particularly interesting for: 1) Soft films, where measuring crack length or perimeter is difficult and, 2) Thin films, where free-standing condition cannot be achieved in purest form. Therefore, K_{IC} directly depends on the product $P\sigma_{ys}^3$, which is larger for stiff polymers that in turn depends upon the curing.

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APPENDIX

A.1. Mechanism

K_{IC} is the stress intensity factor (K_I) at critical level. K_I is determined depending upon the crack mechanism. When $K_I < K_{IC}$, the crack is stable and when $K_I = K_{IC}$, fracture occurs. The unit of $K_I = K_C = K_{IC}$ is $\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$.

Fig. d.1. Different modes of crack opening

As shown in Fig. d.1, K_I , K_{II} and K_{III} can be determined independently. These are defined from the crack tip elements (D.P. Rooke and D.J. Cartwright, 1976) as illustrated in Fig. d.2.

Fig. d.2. Crack tip element

In mixed mode cracking, K_{IC} is determined by relating K from all modes, even though K_I is dominant. This is called as fracture criterion (G. C. Sih and B. Macdonald, 1974). With r = radius and x , y and z = coordinates:

$$K_I = \lim_{r \rightarrow 0} \sqrt{2\pi r} \sigma_{yy}(r, 0) \quad (9)$$

$$K_{II} = \lim_{r \rightarrow 0} \sqrt{2\pi r} \sigma_{yx}(r, 0) \quad (10)$$

$$K_{III} = \lim_{r \rightarrow 0} \sqrt{2\pi r} \sigma_{yz}(r, 0) \quad (11)$$

$$K_{IC}^2 = K_I^2 + K_{II}^2 + \frac{E}{2\mu(1-\nu^2)} K_{III}^2 \quad (12)$$

where μ = shear modulus, ν = Poisson's ratio, K_I = mode 1 K – tensile, K_{II} = mode 2 K – in plane shear and K_{III} = mode 3 K – out of plane shear.

The strain energy release rate (G) can be universally expressed as,

$$G = \beta K \quad (13)$$

where $\beta = \left[\frac{1}{E}\right]$, $\left[\frac{1-\nu^2}{E}\right]$ or $\left[\frac{1}{2\mu}\right]$ depending on the modes and $K = K_I$ or K_{II} or K_{III} . Similar to K_{IC} , G can be determined by summing different modes. The unit of G is KJ/m².

Fig. d.5. Plastic zone approximation

A.2. Nanoindentation

The crack inter-distance 'a' is measured from the imprint of the indent (Fig. d.3), which are expressed as a function of depth. This in turn is substituted in Eq. 2 to determine K.

Fig. d.3. Imprint from nanoindentation

A.3. Plastic zone size

In crack tip plasticity theory (as illustrated in Fig. d.4), the crack propagates from the tip (energy dissipation), which increases with crack growth. Region around the tip is the plastic zone, where the inelastic process occurs.

Fig. d.4. Crack onset

At the onset of crack, $K_I = K_{IC}$, where $r_p \propto \frac{K_{IC}}{\sigma_{ys}^2}$ = measure of material ductility, where r_p = plastic zone from first approximation. By the notional crack concept (Fig. d.5 – second approximation), the plastic zone size is given by Eq.4 [4, 5].

In indentation, the plastic zone increases in size with deformation, which signifies that the load-controlled indentation depth is directly proportional to the increase in plastic zone size (as illustrated in Fig. d.6). When the plastic zone is fully formed i.e. spreading outwards from the indenter, elastic strains has only secondary effects. By Johnson's model, the relationship is given by: [6]

Fig. d.6. Plastic zone distribution in indentation

$$\left[\frac{c}{a_s}\right]^{1/3} = \frac{1}{3 \tan \theta} \frac{E}{\sigma_{ys}} \quad (14)$$

where a_s = imprint radius and θ = semi-apical angle of a conical indenter.

Eq.14 is an indentation model that requires the definition of a hydrostatic core to act as spherical cavity inflation. Therefore, a simple interpretation of Johnson's spherical cavity gives the plastic zone size as in Eq.5.

Eq.5 was broadly validated and expressed as [6],

$$\frac{c}{a_s} = \left[\frac{E \tan \delta}{6 \sigma_{ys} (1 - \nu)} + \frac{2}{3} \left(\frac{1 - 2\nu}{1 - \nu} \right)^{1/3} \right] \quad (15)$$

where ν = Poisson's ratio and δ = angle between indenter flank and surface.